

Project Title	Blue-Cloud 2026: A federated European FAIR and Open Research Ecosystem for oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters
Project Acronym	Blue-Cloud 2026
Project Number	101094227
Type of project	RIA – Research and Innovation Action
Topics	HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01
Starting date of Project	01 January 2023
Duration of the project	42 months
Website	www.blue-cloud.org

D7.2 – Individual Exploitation Plans of Virtual Labs

Work Package	WP7 Exploitation, Roadmap to 2030, and Sustainability
Task	T7.2 Developing an exploitation plan for Blue-Cloud’s assets
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Version	V1.0
Due Date	31/12/2024
Submission Date	16/12/2024

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-RES. Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-CON. Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)

Version History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	01/03/2024	Patricia Cabrera (VLIZ)	Table of Contents & Executive Summary
0.2	29/03/2024	Patricia Cabrera (VLIZ)	Included VLab descriptions
0.3	15/07/2024	Julia Vera (SSBE)	Updated Table of Contents
0.4	22/07/2024	Julia Vera (SSBE)	Added Section 2
0.5	26/07/2024	Julia Vera (SSBE)	Input to all sections with information gathered during workshops
0.6	12/09/2024	Cyrielle Delvenne (VLIZ)	Updated Section 1 and Sections 3-10, with information gathered during meetings and workshops
0.7	01/12/2024	Julien Barde (IRD), Alexander Barth (ULiège), Steven Pint (VLIZ), Abel Dechenne (ULiège), João Vitorino (IH), Francesco Palermo (CCMC), Simona Simoncelli (INGV), Catalina Reyes (OGS), Alessandra Giorgetti (OGS), Enrique Castrillo (SOCIB), Yannis Marketakis (FORTH), Vânia Lima (IH)	Review by VLab leaders and partners
0.8	09/12/2024	Dick Schaap (MARIS), Marine Vernet (IFREMER), Pasquale Pagano (CNR)	Internal review
0.9	16/12/202	Cyrielle Delvenne (VLIZ)	Applied modifications based on review
1.0	19/12/2024	Sara Pittonet (Trust-IT)	Quality check

Glossary of terms

Item	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
BDIs	Blue Data Infrastructures
CCP	Cloud Container Platform
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
CNR	Italian National Research Council
DD&AS	Data Discovery & Access Service
D4Science Infrastructure	Data Infrastructure promoting Open Science (managed by CNR)
DIVAnd	Data interpolating variational analysis in n dimensions
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EMB	European Marine Board
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOVs	Essential Ocean Variables
EU HFR	European High Frequency Radar Node
GRSF	Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries
HF	High-Frequency
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System
KER	Key Exploitable Result
MEI	Marine Environmental Indicators
MPA	Marine Protected Area
NRT	Near-Real-Time
QC	Quality Control
RFMO	Regional Fisheries Management Organisations
SSI	Enhanced Storm Severity
TBD	To Be Defined
TRIX	Trophic State Index
VLab	Virtual Laboratory
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WB	Workbench
WP	Work Package

Keywords

EOSC; Virtual Labs; Big Data; Virtual Research Environment; Data infrastructures

Disclaimer

The Blue-Cloud 2026 project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101094227. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Blue-Cloud 2026 builds upon the pilot Blue-Cloud project, which established a pilot cyber platform that provides researchers access to multi-disciplinary datasets from observations, analytical services, and computing facilities essential for blue science.

The Blue-Cloud open science platform developed a collaborative environment where different services are available. A **data discovery and access service** was developed as an overarching service to facilitate smart sharing of multi-disciplinary datasets with human and machine users. The Blue-Cloud **Virtual Research Environment (VRE)** orchestrates the computing and analytical services in specific integrated and managed applications exploiting federated Blue-Cloud data resources as well as external data resources. In Blue-Cloud 2026, this innovation potential is being further explored and unlocked by **five dedicated demonstrators**. These demonstrators have established Virtual Labs (VLabs) co-designed with top-level marine researchers to demonstrate the power of the Blue-Cloud open science platform to advance marine knowledge, in support of the EU Mission “Restore Our Ocean & Waters by 2030” and the UN Agenda 2030 “Sustainable Development Goals” (SDGs).

This document outlines the roadmap to exploit the VLabs as **Key Exploitable Results** of the Blue Cloud 2026 project, including the data products and services generated within each VLab and therefore ensuring effective dissemination and application of the VLab outputs to various stakeholders and EU Infrastructures. As part of WP7 activities, and namely **Task 7.2 “Developing an exploitation plan for Blue-Cloud’s assets”** [M24-M36] of the work plan of the action, it describes the individual exploitation plans of key Blue-Cloud data services, by identifying their Target Users, establishing effective pathways to disseminate these products beyond the Blue-Cloud 2026 Consortium, and outlining measures towards improving the findability of the products, fostering collaboration and engagement among stakeholders, and ensuring that the project’s outcomes have a broad and beneficial impact. This document will serve as a framework for ongoing analysis, discussions, and identification of critical elements that need to be addressed during the remainder of the project, incorporating input and feedback from all partners, and informing the **Blue-Cloud Exploitation Plan (D7.3)** and the **Blue-Cloud Sustainability Strategy & Plan (D7.5)**.

This document is structured in ten sections. Section 1 introduces the goal of this document. Section 2 covers the exploitation strategy for the Virtual Labs. Section 3 to section 7 cover all the Virtual labs individually including description of the VLab, asset owners, target users, exploitations pathways, exploitation measures and additional resources needed. Section 8 explains how Key Performance Indicators will be quantified. Section 9 explains the link between some Virtual labs and Work Benches. Section 10 summarises the main findings and next steps.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Objective & scope of this document	9
2	Exploitation strategy for Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs.....	10
2.1	Identification of Key Exploitable Results	12
2.2	Exploitation channels prioritised	12
3	KER #4 VLAB 1 “Integration of Coastal Oceans Observations along Europe”	14
3.1	Description and characterisation of the KER	14
3.1.1	KER #4.1. Transboundary processes and connectivity along the European margins 14	
3.1.2	KER #4.2. Extreme events.....	16
3.1.3	KER #4.3. Ocean glider advanced data products.....	17
3.2	Asset owner(s)	18
3.3	Target Users	18
3.4	Exploitation pathways & milestones.....	21
3.5	Exploitation measures committed & planned	24
3.6	What resources would be needed to make this exploitation possible?.....	25
4	KER #5 VLAB 2 “Coastal currents from observations”	26
4.1	Description and characterisation of the KER	26
4.2	Asset owner(s)	27
4.3	Target Users	27
4.4	Exploitation pathways & milestones.....	29
4.5	Exploitation measures committed & planned	31
4.6	What resources would be needed to make this exploitation possible?.....	32
5	KER #6 VLAB 3 « Carbon-Plankton dynamics »	33
5.1	Description and characterisation of the KER	33
5.2	Asset owner(s)	34
5.3	Target Users	35
5.4	Exploitation pathways & milestones.....	37
5.5	Exploitation measures committed & planned	38
5.6	Resources needed to implement the Exploitation Plan	39
6	KER #7 VLAB 4 “Marine Environmental Indicators”	39
6.1	Description and characterisation of the KER	39

6.1.1 KER #7.1. “Ocean Heat Content (OHC)”41

6.1.2 KER #7.2. “Marine Heat Wave (MHW)”41

6.1.3 KER #7.3. “Trophic Index (TRIX)”42

6.1.4 KER #7.4. “Enhanced Storm Severity Index V2 (SSI V2) ”43

6.2 Asset owner(s)44

6.3 Target Users44

6.4 Exploitation pathways & milestones.....46

6.5 Exploitation measures committed & planned47

7 KER #8 VLAB 5 “Global Fisheries Atlas”49

7.1 Description and characterisation of the KER49

7.2 Asset owner(s)49

7.3 Target Users50

7.4 Exploitation pathways & milestones.....52

7.5 Exploitation measures committed & planned54

7.6 Resources needed to implement the Exploitation Plan55

8 Key Performance Indicators and Targets (2026-2030)56

9 Joint opportunities for exploitation across Blue-Cloud KERs59

9.1 Joint exploitation opportunities across Blue-Cloud V Labs.....59

9.2 Joint exploitation with Blue-Cloud Workbenches60

10 Conclusion61

11 Bibliography61

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1. VLab 1 Target users.....	18
Figure 2. VLab 1 Exploitation pathways	21
Figure 3. VLab 1 Exploitation measures from 2024 to 2030	25
Figure 4. Vlab 2 Target users.....	27
Figure 5. VLab 2 Exploitation pathways	29
Figure 6. VLab 2 Exploitation measures from 2024 to 2030	32
Figure 7. Vlab 3 Target users.....	35
Figure 8. Vlab 3 Exploitation pathways	37
Figure 9. VLab 3 Exploitation measures from 2024 to 2030	39
Figure 10. VLab 4 workflow.....	40
Figure 11. VLab 4 Target users.....	44
Figure 12. Vlab 4 Exploitation pathways	46
Figure 13. Vlab 4 Exploitation measures from 2024 to 2030	48
Figure 14. VLab 5 Target users.....	50
Figure 15. Vlab 5 Exploitation pathways	52
Figure 16. Vlab 5 Exploitation measures from 2024 to 2030	55
Figure 17. Users use of the platform for one of the VLab. Users are categorized by countries, by platform they're using, by duration of use.....	58
Figure 18. Adapted from Data Value Chain (Simoncelli et al., 2022).....	60

TABLE OF TABLES

Table 1. KER #4.1. Exploited Data Products.....	15
Table 2. KER #4.2. data product metadata to be exploited	16
Table 3. KER #4.3. data product metadata to be exploited	17
Table 4. Metadata of VLab 2 data product to be exploited	26
Table 5. Metadata of VLab 3 data product to be exploited	33
Table 6. Metadata of OHC data product to be exploited.....	41
Table 7. Metadata of MHW data product to be exploited.....	42
Table 8. Metadata of TRIX data product to be exploited.....	42
Table 9. Metadata of SSI V2 data product to be exploited.....	43
Table 10. Metadata of VLab 5 data product to be exploited.....	49

1 Objective & scope of this document

This document delivers the **Blue-Cloud 2026 Individual Exploitation Plans of Virtual Labs**. It outlines the current understanding of the existing work undertaken by several Blue-Cloud 2026 demonstrators (namely those being developed under Work Package 4 - WP4) and sets forth a plan to exploit the Key Exploitable Results emerging from such work. It will serve as a framework for ongoing analysis, discussions, and identification of critical elements that need to be addressed during the remainder of the project, incorporating input and feedback from all partners, and informing the **Blue-Cloud Exploitation Plan (D7.3)** and the **Blue-Cloud Sustainability Strategy & Plan (D7.5)**. The ultimate goal of these plans is twofold: firstly, to establish a model for exploiting and operating the Blue-Cloud results with the collaboration of partners in the years following the project's conclusion; and secondly, to explore pathways for long-term sustainability of Blue-Cloud's efforts. It aligns with and supports the development of the Blue-Cloud Roadmap 2030. Additionally, emphasising sustainability will encourage partners to commit to and support the planned short-term operation and exploitation of the project's results.

The need for a joined, web-based platform that supports open science is crucial in today's European scientific community. The connection between data collectors (e.g. research institutions), marine scientists (e.g. academics, domain researchers) and users (e.g. governments, RFMOs) is constantly challenged. By agreeing to create platforms where scientists, researchers, software developers and innovators can work together, a bridge is provided to connect different stakeholders closer together, which offers opportunities to improve the delivery of data to scientists, and enhanced data visualisation to data collectors and governments. They can then make efficient and right decisions based on real data and meaningful data analysis. The pilot Horizon 2020 "**Blue-Cloud**" project demonstrated the potential of Open Science in the marine domain. The Horizon Europe "Blue-Cloud 2026" project builds on its results, offering more pathways to link scientists from all around Europe to connect and to create shared platforms where data can be analysed and visualised. The VLabs developed by these projects cover a set of marine multidisciplinary data from "blue" data infrastructures (BDIs) and other marine Research Infrastructures (RIs), like the **Joint European Research Infrastructure for Coastal Observatories (JERICO)**. These data may be from different types and origins and are usually not gathered (coastal and open sea data, plankton, hydrodynamics and fisheries data). The VLabs innovative services, in the form of data products and/or analytical tools, demonstrate the added-value of web-based open science as promoted by European Ocean Science Cloud (EOSC). VLab 1 implements an environment that is specifically designed to widely expand user's ability to access, integrate and exploit observations collected along the European coastal ocean areas, with particular focus on the observations provided by the partners of the Joint European Research Infrastructure for Coastal Observatories (JERICO-RI). VLab 2 provides a service to

generate integrated ocean surface current maps from direct and indirect current measurements derived from different sources, High Frequency (HF) radar. These two VLabs are newly developed in Blue-Cloud 2026, while the next ones (VLabs 3 to 5) were first developed in the previous Blue-Cloud project and are expanded during this new phase. VLab 3 provides a service to analyse the relative contribution of the drivers in phytoplankton dynamics in the Belgium part of the North Sea and the northern Adriatic Sea. Vlab 4 aims to develop a web application that allows users to monitor and assess the environmental status of marine areas, by performing online spatio-temporal analysis with the implemented algorithms, for selected environmental variables. The fifth VLab's mission is to help make fisheries data FAIR and, by doing so, to provide a more comprehensive view of global fisheries to support informed decision-making and management of fisheries resources.

The development of the VLabs includes several tasks and phases, from data collection and processing to the development of analytical services and the publication of the results in the Blue-Cloud Data and Service Catalogue and EOSC Catalogues.

2 Exploitation strategy for Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs

The core objective of Work Package (WP4) of the Blue-Cloud 2026 project “**Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs for demonstrating cross-domain web-based open science**” is to design, manage and run **Virtual Labs (VLabs)** in the **Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE)**, demonstrating the added-value that Blue-Cloud brings to the marine knowledge value chain, and its contribution to relevant EU policy objectives. As part of this work, five VLabs are being developed. Each VLab offers specific data products and tools within the VRE that are easy to use and reproduce by a wider audience. Each of these VLabs has been defined as a **Key Exploitable Result** of the Blue Cloud 2026 project and is meant to be made available to various users beyond the project Consortium for use, exploitation and long-term impact. This objective aligns with the **Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030**, which establishes a long-term vision, a mission, and five strategic paths of action for the evolution of Blue-Cloud, namely:

- **Strategic Action Path 1:** Sustain the flow of FAIR and open marine data into Blue-Cloud.
- **Strategic Action Path 2:** Trigger the development of innovative data analytics methods around priority environmental thematic to inspire and guide the Blue-Cloud community towards further evolving applications in support of key policy objectives.
- **Strategic Action Path 3:** (Further) Federate with key marine data, research and e-infrastructures and strategic initiatives (e.g., EOSC, EDITO-Infra) to enhance value to users.

- **Strategic Action Path 4:** (Further) Grow a thriving ocean open science community, leveraging skills, incentives and rewards and promoting wide dissemination of FAIR methods incubated in Blue-Cloud to boost innovation at a broader scale.
- **Strategic Action Path 5:** Connect and align with broader developments and other communities to contribute to a European and a global, international knowledge system in support of the EU Green Deal and the UN Agenda 2030.

The Virtual Labs fall within Strategic Action Path 2, showcasing the value of developing specific, innovative data analytics methods around priority environmental thematic (see section 2.1). A common **exploitation strategy** has been devised for all V Labs, clustering all exploitation measures around three core channels to contribute across the above strategic action paths, namely:

- Exploitation via the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment;
- Exploitation via European and international marine data services and aggregators;
- Exploitation via the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC);
- Exploitation via the European Digital Twin of the Ocean.

In order to better describe this exploitation strategy, each VLab has been assigned an individual Exploitation Plan, structured as follows:

1. VLab Description and Characterisation of the KER

This section provides a brief overview of the VLab, including a description of its services. The VLab itself is considered a Key Exploitable Result (KER #X), with each of its services categorized as sub-KERs (KER #X.1)

2. Asset owners

This section identifies the developer’s entities responsible for the VLab.

3. Target users

Here, we define the different user groups that interact with the VLab's services. Primary users are those who directly engage with the services, while intermediary users act as a bridge between primary users and the VLab. The final consumers—end users—represent the ultimate target audience of the VLab.

4. Exploitation pathways & milestones

To reach the target users, we have identified several exploitation pathways, grouped into four categories:

- Community engagement
- Outreach Initiatives
- Collaboration

- Data catalogues

5. Exploitation measures

This section outlines specific milestones and timelines for implementing the identified exploitation pathways. These measures are designed to ensure the effective deployment and utilization of VLab' services.

6. Resources Needed

Additional resources required to implement the exploitation measures are listed here.

The goal of these exploitation measures is to address existing challenges, seize new opportunities, and maximize the VLab's impact. By focusing on practical applicability and broad user uptake, we aim to ensure the successful exploitation of the VLab's outputs.

2.1 Identification of Key Exploitable Results

The Blue-Cloud 2026 project features two different types of “demonstrators”, namely “Workbenches” and “Virtual Labs”. Specifically, Blue-Cloud 2026 is developing three Workbenches (KER #1, KER #2, and KER #3, respectively), and five Virtual Labs (KER #4, KER #5, KER #6, KER #7, and KER #8, respectively). As the focus of this document is on the Virtual Labs, the following Key Exploitable Results (KER) are covered in this document:

- VLab 1. “Integration of Coastal observations along Europe” - KER #4
- VLab 2. “Coastal Currents from Observations” - KER #5
- VLab 3. “Carbon Plankton Dynamics” - KER #6
- VLab 4. “Marine Environmental Indicators” - KER #7
- VLab 5. “Global Fisheries Atlas” - KER #8

2.2 Exploitation channels prioritised

As earlier introduced, when defining exploitation objectives and measures for Blue-Cloud 2026 KERs, three specific channels have been prioritised towards long-term impact, as part of a common exploitation strategy:

- **Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment:** The Blue-Cloud VRE is the primary exploitation channel for any of the Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs and the data products and applications they offer. The VLabs offer (open, reproducible) resources of interest to the marine research and innovation community, which can be leveraged to further develop added-value applications for other (secondary or tertiary) users. Sustaining the exploitation of available VLabs supports the objective of growing a thriving community of open science practitioners in the marine domain, which is one of the overarching

objectives of the Blue-Cloud ecosystem of services. A rich and diverse portfolio of VLabs further contributes to enhance the attractiveness of the Blue-Cloud platform and will be considered as a pivotal element of its exploitation strategy and plan (D7.3 – Joint Exploitation Plan), which will be shaped and delivered by December 2025.

- **European and international marine data services and aggregators:** Identified in Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030 as “intermediate, secondary users”, European marine data services such as EMODnet and Copernicus Marine Service offer a win-win, publishing channel for Blue-Cloud’s VLabs resulting data products. As part of its value proposition, Blue-Cloud seeks to enhance the interoperability of marine data to accelerate the transformation of marine data to products, in support of marine knowledge. Ingesting Blue-Cloud’s data products into European, long-term marine data services and aggregators ensures wide dissemination to a much broader user base (SMEs, industry, policy makers, NGOs, etc.) than currently Blue-Cloud’s, ensuring they can be reused, activated and applied by researchers and innovators to deliver to the needs of decision makers in support of wider economic, societal and policy developments. The same logic applies to leveraging other data aggregators and services, whether European or international, as relevant, for broader dissemination.
- **The European Digital Twin Ocean:** The European Digital Twin Ocean (DTO) is a high-resolution, multi-dimensional, and near real-time digital representation of the ocean. Designed to be accessible to citizens, scientists, entrepreneurs, and policymakers, it will provide innovative tools to transform the way we understand, manage and interact with the ocean. Blue-Cloud is positioned as an incubator for the DTO. By leveraging the alignment efforts of Blue-Cloud 2026 and EDITO -the public infrastructure of the European DTO, which is orchestrated through the Blue-Cloud DTO task force, the integration of the VLabs into the EDITO platform will enhance their interoperability and outreach, enabling these resources to be combined with global ocean observation data, advanced modeling and AI tools on high-performance computing platforms to support dynamic ocean simulations scenarios and decision-making tools. Alignment of EDITO with other relevant European and international initiatives (DestinationEarth, DITTO, respectively) will extend the outreach and allow transdisciplinary uses.
- **The European Open Science Cloud:** EOSC is growing and consolidating as the European data space for the academic, scientific and research community in Europe. Since its inception, Blue-Cloud has been conceived as the thematic “marine” component of EOSC, setting up and offering services seeking to bridge and connect the marine community with relevant EOSC developments, i.e., the **EOSC EU Node**, the platform officially launched in October 2024 to support multi-disciplinary and multi-national

research promoting the use of FAIR data and supplementary services in Europe and beyond. The emerging development of the EOSC EU Node and complementary thematic nodes opens new opportunities to further anchor Blue-Cloud's position as a marine thematic open science node servicing the EOSC community. With this in mind, all VLabs will consider and seek to leverage exploitation opportunities via EOSC, tailoring measures to their respective, specific thematic landscape, as relevant (e.g., seeking synergies with other ongoing EOSC projects, disciplines, etc).

The specific exploitation measures devised for each channel are further described in the Individual Exploitation Plans of the VLabs, respectively (see Sections 3-7).

3 KER #4 VLAB 1 “Integration of Coastal Oceans Observations along Europe”

3.1 Description and characterisation of the KER

This VLab implements an environment specifically designed to support users in their explorations of the available *coastal* ocean information, developing and implementing tools to facilitate access to different types of data, to data processing and quality control when needed, to exploitation of individual datasets and to integrated analysis and visualisation of various types of data. It will bring together available data from international data repositories with other observations collected by partners of the Joint European Research Infrastructure for Coastal Observatories (**JERICO-RI**) to deliver three Key Exploitable Results (KER), namely:

- **KER #4.1.** addresses “**Transboundary processes and connectivity along the European margins**”, focusing on processes such as biological connectivity, contaminants spread, and along margin impacts of river outflows.
- **KER #4.2.** “**Extreme Events**” focuses on coastal impacts of major storms.
- **KER #4.3.** “**Ocean glider**” shows the added value of repeated glider sections.

3.1.1 KER #4.1. “Transboundary processes and connectivity along the European margins”

This service focuses on “**Transboundary Transport and Connectivity along the European Margins**”. It explores the potential of integrating *in situ* and remote observations with numerical model results to enhance our understanding of transboundary processes in the European coastal ocean. The aim is to better understand these processes and their potential impacts, such as biological connectivity and the spread of contaminants. The outcome of this service is a **Dashboard Environment** designed for **Data Selection, Processing, Exploration, Integration,**

and Visualization. Table 1 provides detailed metadata for the products generated during the use of this VLab. The data, sourced from aggregators such as CMEMS, can be seamlessly imported into the VLab environment for direct analysis. Users can apply a range of available analytical methods, including basic statistical analyses, to gain insights from the data.

Table 1. KER #4.1. Exploited Data Products

Input datasets	Available from data aggregators such as CMEMS, EU HF Radar Node, EMODNET, C3S) and JERICO-RI partners (SOCIB data repository, Puertos del Estado observations, PLOCAN glider section). It comprises data from HF radar stations, multiparametric buoys, wave buoys, gliders, coastal tide gauges, remote sensing products and model results (e.g. NEMO, ERA5). <i>Full description provided in D4.1 (VLabs Technical Requirements).</i>
Analysis method	Data exploration tools available to the user: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic Statistics for individual variables/datasets, • Correlation Analysis, Integration tools: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modal Decomposition • Data Intercomparison • Variability Structure • Transport of different properties Advanced Integration tools: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coastal Ocean Response
Spatial resolution	Dependent on the Data Sets selected by the user (typical spatial resolutions of order 1km and 10km)
Temporal coverage	Dependent on the Data Sets selected by the user, global period from 1980 to present.
Temporal resolution	Dependent on the Data Sets selected by user (typical time resolutions of order 1 hours and 1 day)
Variables (unit)	Surface and subsurface Currents (cm/s), Surface and subsurface Temperature (°C), Surface and subsurface Salinity, Seas Surface Height (m), sedimentary and biological variables to be defined.
Output file format	NetCDF, ASCII
Product relevance	Coastal ocean researchers focused on shelf/slope processes and interactions with rivers or deep ocean, coastal modelers, data scientists, Blue Economy sectors (particularly aquaculture, and fisheries), Environmental Managers (e.g. MPAs managers). Crisis managers (particularly SAR or contaminant accidents such as oil-spills, invasive species), stakeholders, policymakers

3.1.2 KER #4.2. Extreme events

This service focuses on characterising the expression of extreme events affecting the European margin and evaluating its impacts on the coastal ocean environment. It will provide a **Dashboard Environment** for **Data Selection, Processing, Exploration, Integration and Visualisation**. Table 2 details the metadata of VLab-generated products, which can be imported from sources like CMEMS for direct analysis using methods such as basic statistics.

Table 2. KER #4.2. data product metadata to be exploited

Input datasets	Available from different data aggregators such as CMEMS, EU HF Radar Node, EMODNET, C3S and JERICO-RI partners (Puertos del Estado observations). Comprises data from multiparametric and wave buoys, HF radar stations, coastal tide gauges, remote sensing products and model results (e.g.WaveWatch3). <i>Full description provided in D4.1 (VLabs Technical Requirements).</i>
Analysis method	Data exploration tools available to the user: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic Statistics for individual variables/datasets, • Correlation Analysis, Integration tools: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Intercomparison • Variability Structure • Impacts on bottom sedimentary cover
Spatial resolution	Dependent on the Data Sets selected by the user (typical spatial resolutions of order 1km and 10km)
Temporal coverage	Dependent on the Data Sets selected by the user, global period from 1980 to present
Temporal resolution	Dependent on the Data Sets selected by user (typical time resolutions of order 1 sec, 1hour and 1 day)
Variables (unit)	Wave parameters, Meteorological Parameters, Surface and Subsurface Currents, Sedimentary Cover.
Output file format	NetCDF, ASCII
Product relevance	Coastal ocean researchers focused on coastal erosion and impacts of extreme storms in shelf ecosystems or on climate change, coastal modelers, data scientists, Blue Economy sectors (particularly aquaculture, energy sector, coastal engineering), Environmental Managers, Crisis managers (particularly impacts of extreme storms in coastal populations), stakeholders, policymakers

3.1.3 KER #4.3. Ocean glider advanced data products

This service offers a **processing toolbox** designed to generate interpolated profiles on a regular grid along the **glider monitoring line**, based on the vertical and horizontal resolution of the raw data. It includes vertical sections of key parameters such as potential temperature, practical salinity, potential density, and geostrophic velocity (meridional component only) within the **Ibiza Channel**.

Additionally, the service provides **software libraries** and **Jupyter notebooks** for processing user data and facilitating data integration. An **Advanced Data Viewer** will also be available for enhanced data exploration and visualization. Table 3 details the metadata of VLab-generated products, which can be imported from sources like SOCIB’s thredds data server for direct analysis using methods such as basic statistics.

Table 3. KER #4.3. data product metadata to be exploited

Input datasets	Input file access: SOCIB’s thredds data server (a) RAW datasets from Slocum glider missions and (b) OG1.0 datasets from Slocum glider missions
Analysis method	Basic Statistics, Correlation Analysis, Interpolation of some variables, Transport of different properties, Data Intercomparison
Spatial coverage	Balearic sea
Spatial resolution	Dependent on the Data Sets provided by the user. Typical missions resolution is around 3 months, and minimum time resolution will adapt to the transect duration
Temporal coverage	Dependent on the Data Sets provided by the user. From the first Slocum Glider mission to the present day.
Temporal resolution	Dependent on the Data Sets provided by the user. Typical missions duration is around 3 months, and minimum time resolution will adapt to the transect duration
Variables (unit)	Initial date (yyyymmdd), end date (yyyymmdd), Bounding box coordinates (Lat_1, Long_1, Lat_2, Long_2), smooth parameter (Km), criterion for WIW detection (fixed-range/geometry)
Output file format	NetCDF (OG1.0 format), PNG, NPY
Standard vocabularies	OceanGliders Parameter Usage Vocabulary
Product relevance	Coastal ocean researchers focused on physical and biogeochemical observations, as well as derived dynamic geostrophic transports, coastal modelers, data scientists.

3.2 Asset owner(s)

The asset owners of this VLab are **Instituto Hidrografico (IH)** in Lisbon, Portugal, **Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers France (IEEE)**, France and **Balearic Islands Coastal Ocean Observing and Forecasting System (SOCIB)**, Spain.

3.3 Target Users

Figure 1. VLab 1 Target users

VLab 1 is designed to serve a diverse range of user groups, categorized into primary/intermediary, and tertiary users, each benefiting from the platform’s unique capabilities in marine science and data integration (Figure 1).

Primary users can be categorized into distinct groups based on their specific roles and interactions with the system, including marine researchers, facilitators, and data catalogues, each with unique needs and objectives.

Marine researchers

VLab 1 is dedicated to significantly enhancing the capabilities of coastal modelers, data scientists, and marine researchers. It provides a purpose-built platform for processing, exploring, and integrating diverse datasets critical to the European coastal ocean environment. Through the platform, researchers can generate customized, integrated datasets by selecting input sources from various **Blue Data Infrastructures (BDIs)**, defining target regions, specifying analysis timeframes, and applying rigorous quality controls. This streamlined approach empowers users to tackle complex coastal challenges with greater precision and efficiency.

Facilitators

VLab 1 can be used as a **training ground** for **scientists** in open science data and tools, particularly benefiting students in oceanography, marine biology, and related disciplines, as well as those in data analysis and computer sciences.

Data catalogues

The platform will produce datasets derived from the implementation of a toolbox for Slocum glider missions in the OG1.0 format. This represents a crucial step toward ensuring the seamless integration of standardised datasets into the **Global Disaster Alert and Coordination Systems (GDACs)**. These datasets will adhere to best practices as outlined by the **Ocean Best Practices System (OBPS)** and will be complemented by resources from **the Copernicus Marine Open Data, EU HF Radar Node, EMODnet Data Products, and SeaDataNet**, potentially enhancing their catalogues with Blue Cloud data products.

Further building on the work of VLab 1, other (**tertiary**) users will benefit from its tools & services:

Policy makers

For **policy makers** and EU initiatives, such as the **EU Mission Restore Oceans 2030** and the **Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)**, VLab 1 offers essential tools for managing **marine protected areas (MPAs)** and implementing **Essential Ocean Variables (EOV)** through programs like the **Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS)**.

Blue Economy

Stakeholders from aquaculture, fisheries, and the energy sector (including offshore wind and wave energy) will benefit from enhanced predictions of wave, wind, and currents patterns. Additionally, industries involved in outdoor activities and coastal erosion management, such as cable-laying companies, stand to gain from the predictive tools provided by VLab 1.

Crisis response managers

They will find value in the integration products and advanced visualisation tools that VLab 1 offers, enabling them to identify key drivers and analyse potential scenarios for specific geographic areas. Non-governmental organisations (NGOs) focused on marine debris management and search & rescue operations can utilise these visualisation tools—such as those in BlueCloud 2026—to aid in locating lost items at sea, providing directional guidance based on surface currents rather than precise locations.

Furthermore, ongoing reporting activities, including the Copernicus Marine Service Ocean State Report, BAMS State of Climate, and IPCC assessments, can utilise resulting Blue-Cloud 2026 VLab datasets to maintain up-to-date monitoring indicators, supporting informed decision-making and policy development.

3.4 Exploitation pathways & milestones

Figure 2. VLab 1 Exploitation pathways

To ensure the Blue-Cloud 2026 platform is readily accessible to identified target users, as outlined in Section 3.3, various measures will be implemented to address barriers and enhance engagement (Figure 2).

VLab Access and Support

First, VLab 1 will be **open** to any user beyond the Blue-Cloud Consortium during and after Blue-Cloud 2026. Support will be offered to users of the VLab during Blue-Cloud 2026, and for two years after project-end, supported and funded by another Horizon Europe (HE) project, namely HE **AQUARIUS**. This support includes a helpdesk for VLab users, improvement of selected modules and webinars (KER #4.1. and #4.2.). IH commits to allocating two researchers with a dedication of 2 PMs/year to support users of service 1 and 2 during two years after project-end. For KER #4.3., support will be provided when possible after project end.

Community Engagement

Researchers may encounter challenges such as limited familiarity with the Blue-Cloud platform, its specific data products, and cloud-based solutions. Additionally, stakeholders may require diverse types of information and analyses depending on regional and coastal environmental contexts. To address these challenges, the project will implement targeted measures focused on knowledge dissemination and community engagement.

Planned efforts include:

- **Publications:** Scientific articles and webinars will be organized to highlight the capabilities of VLab 1 in advancing coastal ocean research. Key milestones include:
 - A preliminary publication, co-authored by IH, IEEE, and SOCIB, scheduled for release in January 2026.
 - A peer-reviewed scientific paper, to be published in January 2028 by IH, focusing on the application of Key Exploitable Results (KER) #4.1 and #4.2 in the study of interactions between deep-sea, coastal, and inland environments.
- **Blue-Cloud 2026 Webinars & Hackathon:** These events, aimed at the research community, will showcase VLab 1's potential to enhance coastal ocean research and invite further contributions for improvement.
- **Blue-Cloud 2026 Training Academy:** The established **Blue-Cloud Training Academy** will equip students with essential skills and knowledge for coastal ocean research. KER #4.3 will provide training in oceanography (by the scientific team) and user interface usage (by the technological team), with continued training offered by IH after Blue-Cloud 2026.

Outreach Initiatives

IH and IEEE will carry out targeted outreach in select European countries, focusing on key stakeholders involved in the **Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)** monitoring and regional conventions such as OSPAR. In addition, they will engage policymakers from the **Essential Ocean Variables (EOV-GOOS)** National Focal Points, **National Navies**, and **Marine Protected Area (MPA)** managers from various regions.

To strengthen international collaborations, the project will encourage participation in relevant publications and foster partnerships with global research initiatives. This will increase visibility and enhance cooperation across the scientific community. Furthermore, webinars and promotional activities aimed at the blue economy sector, coastal managers, and crisis response professionals

will facilitate deeper engagement with blue economy stakeholders, driving collaborative efforts for sustainable coastal management.

Stakeholders will be shared with VLab 2 and VLab 5, with cross-fertilization explained further in Section 9.

Collaboration

The project will foster direct collaboration with established networks, such as the JERICO-RI community, and associated infrastructures like EMSO-RI and DANUBIUS-RI. These collaborations will strengthen stakeholder involvement and enhance the utility of Blue-Cloud solutions across diverse regional contexts.

Example Collaboration:

KER#4.1 and KER#4.2 are closely articulated with a Pilot Study of integration of observations along the Iberian Atlantic Margin, conducted in collaboration between IH (Portugal), Puertos del Estado (Spain) and PLOCAN (Spain) initiated in the framework of H2020 project JERICO-S3.

Data catalogues

VLab 1 will engage in dissemination activities with data catalogues from EMODnet, CMEMS, Ocean Best Practices Systems (OBPS), and SeaDataNet. Key initiatives include:

- **Processing Toolbox (KER #4.3):** A processing toolbox will be developed to generate datasets from Slocum glider missions in OG1.0 format, enabling integration with the **Global Disaster Alert & Coordination Systems (GDACs)**. All scripts will be available on GitHub after project completion.
- **Data Sharing:** Scripts will be uploaded to **Zenodo** by IH and IEEE, ensuring accessibility for all current and future users. Data products from KER #4.1 and KER #4.2 will be incorporated into **EMODnet Physics** and the **European HFR node**, while KER #4.3 will be added to the EOSC Catalogue.

3.5 Exploitation measures committed & planned

The exploitation measures committed by Consortium partners are outlined in Figure 3. Improvements of selected modules will be made based on the first user's comments. A webinar will be organised in April 2025. Blue-Cloud 2026 will also organise a Hackaton in Autumn 2025 for all the VLabs. Training by IH for KER #4.1. & #4.2. will happen in December 2025, either online or during Blue-Cloud 2026's General Assemblies and project meetings. SOCIB (KER #4.3.) will offer training with the technological and scientific team.

Data products from KER #4.1. and KER #4.2. will be ingested into EMODnet Physics & Biology in 2025, after the release of the beta version of the VLab. This will be linked to projects such as JERICO and AQUARIUS, details still need to be defined by partners.

KER #4.3. will include their output in the EOSC catalogue. Definition of static products is planned for potential ingestion in the **European HFR node**.

Scripts will be published in **GitHUB** by SOCIB at the VLab completion in 2026. All results will be uploaded to Zenodo.

After Blue-Cloud 2026 project

IH plans to publish a peer-reviewed scientific paper in January 2028 focusing on the use of KER #4.1. & #4.2. dedicated to research of interactions between deep-coastal-inland environments. A Youtube video will be available for training.

Committed Exploitation Measures

Figure 3. VLab 1 Exploitation measures from 2024 to 2030

3.6 What resources would be needed to make this exploitation possible?

In order to provide support to users and keep improving selected modules, 3 PMs/year (preferably researcher) would be needed to dedicate support to users and improve the three services offered in VLab 1.

IH commits to allocating two researchers with a dedication of 2 PMs/year to support users of KER #4.1 & #4.2 during 2 years after project-end.

4 KER #5 VLAB 2 “Coastal currents from observations”

4.1 Description and characterisation of the KER

The VLab aims to provide a new service to generate integrated ocean surface current maps from High Frequency (HF) radar, drifter data and geostrophic currents from altimetry data using the **data interpolating variational analysis in n dimensions (DIVAnd) method**. The integration and analysis of these datasets will be carried out using a range of constraints. These include the presence of the coastline, limitations on horizontal divergence, and adherence to a momentum balance (encompassing acceleration, Coriolis force, and surface pressure gradient). This methodology follows the approach detailed in Barth et al. (2021), which resulted from the SeaDataCloud and EMODnet Physics projects. It is expected that different data sources will have a different accuracy, which will be taken into account. The VLab will provide an easy way to use the analysis techniques without installation and with a set of data sources already preconfigured.

The main output of this VLab is a service in the form of easily customizable **Jupyter notebooks** that allow users to generate surface currents maps for a user-chosen coastal region (when data is available, and particularly the availability of HF radar data, which extents depending on the configuration about 50 km - 200 km offshore, Table 4). The user would also be able to make Lagrangian simulations based on these currents maps to visualise the movements of artificial drifters released at a user-chosen location (assuming suitable data coverage). The second service will be an **oil simulation product** in the form of a Jupyter Notebook.

Table 4. Metadata of VLab 2 data product to be exploited

Input datasets	Global Ocean-Delayed Mode in-situ Observations of surface (drifters and HFR) and sub-surface (vessel-mounted ADCPs) water velocity : https://doi.org/10.17882/86236 European Seas Along Track L 3 Sea Surface Heights Reprocessed 1993 Ongoing Tailored For Data Assimilation : https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00139 Near Real Time Surface Ocean Total Velocity by HFR-CALYPSO-Total : University of Malta (Dr Adam Gauci) https://data-erddap.emodnet-physics.eu/erddap/files/HFR_CALYPSO_Total/
Analysis method	Diva interpolation
Spatial coverage	Mediterranean Sea
Spatial resolution	Surface, horizontal resolution is to be defined
Temporal coverage	2015-2025
Temporal resolution	Monthly mean

Variables (unit)	m/s
Output file format	NetCDF-4
Standard vocabularies	NetCDF CF Standard names
Product relevance	Offshore, coastal areas

4.2 Asset owner(s)

The asset owners are **Université de Liège (ULiège)** and **Fondazione Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici - Fondazione (CMCC)**.

4.3 Target Users

Figure 4. Vlab 2 Target users

VLab 2 is an invaluable resource for a broad spectrum of stakeholders involved in ocean research and management (Figure 4). The following sections outline the key user groups, starting with primary users, followed by intermediary users, and concluding with end users.

Marine researchers

Data scientists and coastal ocean modellers, can leverage this platform to enhance their investigations.

Facilitators

Academic researchers and students, may utilise VLab as a training tool to develop competencies in Jupyter, R, and other analytical software.

Data catalogue

Data catalogues within VLab integrates various data sources, including the **Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS)** and **European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF)** wind data, as well as outputs from the Blue-Cloud catalogue and custom user data.

Further building on the work of VLab 2, other (**tertiary**) users will benefit from its tools & services:

Policy makers

This comprehensive data framework is particularly beneficial for policy makers, who can utilise current data to e.g., **assess residence times of pollutants and other materials in marine environments**. Moreover, **practitioners** like local law enforcement and search and rescue teams can rely on current predictions to track debris in water, ensuring timely and effective responses.

Blue Economy and Industry

VLab 2 provides essential tools supporting applications, such as oil spill forecasting, litter tracking, and aquaculture management.

Blue-Cloud EOSC Community

It emphasises the importance of VLab for the validation of ocean models, reinforcing its role as a pivotal resource in advancing marine research and sustainable practices across Europe.

4.4 Exploitation pathways & milestones

Figure 5. VLab 2 Exploitation pathways

To ensure the Blue-Cloud 2026 platform is readily accessible to identified target users, as outlined in Section 4.3, various measures will be implemented to address barriers and enhance engagement (Figure 5).

VLabs Access and Support

VLab 2 will be accessible to any user beyond the Blue-Cloud Consortium, with content available under the GPL license both during and after the project's completion. Support will be provided through GitHub issues to track and address user queries. This support will remain available after the project ends, depending on the availability of funding and at the discretion of the VLab leaders. Requests for support will be evaluated on a case-by-case basis.

Community Engagement

VLab 2 aims to address barriers to access, such as unfamiliarity with the Blue-Cloud infrastructure or integration with existing workflows. This will be achieved through comprehensive documentation, scientific publications, webinars, and training sessions. Training will be part of activities organized by the Blue-Cloud 2026 consortium, including those planned by WP6. If funding permits, training may continue after the project ends.

- **Publications:** Peer-reviewed scientific publications and/or data papers will be submitted for publication in 2025 by the VLab 2 leaders. The exact publication date will be defined by the scientific journal, depending on the review process. An improved version of the code and service will be released later, if necessary, to enhance the platform's functionality. These publications will help disseminate the progress and applications of VLab 2 in marine ecosystem research.
- **Webinars and Other Interactive Sessions:** Webinars and training sessions will be organized to support users in getting started with VLab 2. These events will be publicly available, with a detailed handbook provided to guide users through using the platform. Webinars will address potential barriers to using the platform, especially for non-expert users like policy makers, and will promote the platform's capabilities in advancing marine research.

Outreach Initiatives

The Blue-Cloud 2026 Hackathon will invite a wide range of participants, including marine scientists, data scientists, ICT experts, innovators, students, and ocean enthusiasts, to explore and test the Blue-Cloud Open Science platform. Participants will have the opportunity to develop applications that contribute to advancing ocean literacy, supporting a greener blue economy, and enhancing international collaboration towards the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The hackathon will utilize VLab 2 in combination with other VLabs.

Collaboration

The VLab will encourage collaboration with industries, research groups, and policy makers, including stakeholders from sectors that may require on-premise computing infrastructure. FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles will guide the platform's development, ensuring reproducibility and supporting both cloud-based and local workflows. This will make the platform adaptable to a wide range of users, from researchers to industries. This VLab is still debating additional ways to invite specific, selected communities to test the Virtual Lab. Any new developments will be reflected in the Blue-Cloud Exploitation Plan (D7.3), due in December 2025.

Data Catalogues

To address potential concerns about data privacy and security, VLab 2 will highlight that all environments are private and VLabs credentials will be used for access. Users may also be provided with the option to utilize portable workflows, making the platform more accessible for both cloud and on-premise users. Scripts associated with the platform, including Jupyter notebooks for various steps in the workflow, will be published by ULiege on GitHub in 2025. The workflow is based on the open-source code DIVAnd, and the system will be easily accessible via deep links, similar to how Google Docs or Binder links work.

4.5 Exploitation measures committed & planned

The exploitation measures committed by Consortium partners are outlined in Figure 6. In 2025, this Vlab will be advertised in webinars and training organised by the Blue-Cloud 2026 consortium. It will also be part of the Hackaton in Autumn 2025.

The results will be implemented in Zenodo at the VLab completion in 2026. Results will be integrated in EMODNet Physics.

Figure 6. VLab 2 Exploitation measures from 2024 to 2030

4.6 What resources would be needed to make this exploitation possible?

In order for this VLab to be still available to users after project completion, resources needed are the platform D4Science, access to Jupyter notebooks on the platform and CMEMS data archive. If additional funding is secured, further training activities could be offered after the end of Blue-Cloud 2026.

5 KER #6 VLAB 3 « Carbon-Plankton dynamics »

5.1 Description and characterisation of the KER

Marine phytoplankton is at the base of the marine food web and regulates functions in coastal ecosystems. Changes observed in the marine plankton community are expected to have a knock-on effect throughout the food web and the biogeochemical dynamics of marine ecosystems (and to an extent physical). Therefore, understanding how primary production changes through time and space is of key importance to better quantify the effects of human activities and their impact on the ocean.

The objective of this VLab is to offer a workflow to analyse which factors drive the phytoplankton dynamics and how these factors change in space and time using the Nutrient-Phytoplankton-Zooplankton-Detritus (NPZD) model (Soetaert and Herman, 2009). The workflow is focused on a marine system and follows a similar methodology as described in Everaert et al. (2015). The model is converted to run also in carbon units, allowing one to integrate carbon information (carbonate system concentrations and fluxes from **Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS)** Belgian and Italian stations BE-SOOP-Simon Stevin & BE-FOS-Thornton Buoy, **Piattaforma Avanzata LabOratorio Mare Adriatico (IT-FOS-PALOMA)**, ...) to infer carbon sequestration as part of the detritus state variable. Additionally, the model will be applied with data from the Northern Adriatic Sea to improve the reproducibility of the scripts.

This Vlab has two KER. KER #6.1 is a **biogeochemical model** that can be applied to different regions. The expected results of KER #6.1 are **Jupyter notebooks**. KER #6.2 is the quantification of carbon sequestration and plankton dynamics. It will be presented as **data and scientific manuscript**.

Terms and conditions will imply free, open access to all resources available in the VLab with CC BY licence.

Table 5. Metadata of VLab 3 data product to be exploited

Asset owner	VLIZ	OGS
Input datasets	Nutrients concentration, salinity, seawater temperature, pH, plankton abundances from LifeWatch and EMODnet Chemistry Carbon data from ICOS and SOCAT	Nutrients concentration, salinity, seawater temperature, pH, plankton abundances from EMODnet Biology and EMODnet Chemistry Carbon data from ICOS and SOCAT

Analysis method	Nutrient-phytoplankton-zooplankton-detritus model	Nutrient-phytoplankton-zooplankton-detritus model
Spatial coverage	Belgian Exclusive Economic Zone	Gulf of Trieste, Italy
Temporal coverage	April 2014 to present	2011-2020
Temporal resolution	Daily mean	Daily mean
Variables (unit)	Chlorophyll-a ($\mu\text{g. m}^{-3}$) DIN (mmol N m^{-3}) DIC (mmol C m^{-3}) pCO ₂ in seawater (μatm) Atmosphere-seawater carbon flux ($\text{mmol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$) Relative contribution of determinants ()	Chlorophyll-a ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) DIN (mmol N m^{-3}) DIC (mmol C m^{-3}) pCO ₂ in seawater (μatm) Atmosphere-seawater carbon flux ($\text{mmol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$) Relative contribution of determinants ()
Output file format	CSV	CSV
Product relevance	Carbon sequestration, plankton dynamics, policy makers, climate studies, what-if scenarios	Carbon sequestration, plankton dynamics, policy makers, climate studies, what-if scenarios

5.2 Asset owner(s)

The asset owners are **Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ)** and **Instituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e Geofisica Sperimentale (OGS)**.

5.3 Target Users

Figure 7. Vlab 3 Target users

VLab 3 serves diverse user groups—primary, intermediary, and tertiary—by leveraging its marine science and data integration capabilities. Primary users include marine researchers, facilitators, and data catalogues, each with distinct roles, needs, and objectives.

Marine researchers

Prime target users of this VLab are researchers who are at the forefront of coastal ecosystem studies, utilising advanced modelling techniques to enhance our understanding of carbon dynamics. Key contributors include **ecological modellers**, namely prominent figures from **University of Gent (UGent)**, **Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research (NIOZ)** and the **Biogeochemistry and Earth System Modeling (BGésys)** group from **Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB)** are instrumental in developing models that assess ecological interactions and carbon fluxes.

Facilitators

To ensure that target users can fully leverage the Blue-Cloud resources, specific facilitation measures will be implemented such as the **Blue-Cloud Training Academy**. This initiative will provide training sessions focused on the benefits of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles. By enhancing understanding and accessibility, we aim to empower researchers and stakeholders to utilise available data effectively. Engaging users via the **Blue-Cloud 2026 Hackathon** will foster further innovation and collaboration, generating novel solutions to pressing research questions.

Data catalogues

Current data catalogues, including EMODNet, CMEMS, and SeaDataNet, serve as critical resources for marine data. However, they have notable limitations. These platforms currently do not provide comprehensive information regarding carbon fluxes and their connections with phytoplankton. Additionally, resources like **SOCAT** and the **Sustainable Development Goal 14.3.1. oa.iode.org portal** primarily offer concentrations of CO₂, DIC, total alkalinity, and oxygen, lacking detailed insights into carbon dynamics. This VLab will therefore contribute to bridging this gap.

Further building on the work of VLab 3, other (**tertiary**) users will benefit from its tools & services:

Policy makers

Collaboration with policy makers is essential for translating scientific knowledge into actionable policies. Key initiatives that foster this collaboration include the **European Marine Board (EMB)**, MSFD Descriptors and the Blue Carbon Initiative. By working closely with these entities, we can ensure that research findings inform policy decisions and contribute to sustainable marine management.

European Digital Twin Ocean

Once calibrated and validated, models can simulate various scenarios and assess their impacts on the carbon system and marine ecosystems. These models are crucial for developing a **Digital Twin of the Ocean**, providing a powerful tool for research and policy applications. The integration of advanced modelling capabilities is supported by the various Blue-Cloud task forces seeking to establish collaboration and/or feedback loops into EOSC and EDITO, the public infrastructure of the EU DTO.

5.4 Exploitation pathways & milestones

Figure 8. Vlab 3 Exploitation pathways

To ensure the Blue-Cloud 2026 platform is readily accessible to identified target users, as outlined in Section 5.3, various measures will be implemented to address barriers and enhance engagement (Figure 8).

VLabs Access and Support

VLab 3 will be **accessible to all users**, extending beyond the Blue-Cloud Consortium, with content available under the CC BY-SA 4.0 during and after Blue-Cloud 2026. **Support** will be provided through a **help desk** during the project, and potentially afterwards if funding permits.

Community Engagement

To minimise barriers for new users, such as the time investment needed to get started, **webinars** and **training** sessions will be organised. Priority will be given to direct interactions with **experienced modellers** to enhance the user experience.

- **Publications:** Scientific publications will play a key role in **promoting** VLab 3 to the research community. The first paper was published in July 2023 in the Journal of Marine

Science and Engineering (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse11081510>). A second publication, focused on the BPNS model, is planned for release in 2025, with contributions from researchers in Italy, Slovenia, and Croatia who study plankton and carbon dynamics in the Northern Adriatic.

Outreach Initiatives

It is recognized that a specific use case might limit engagement with a broader range of stakeholders. To address this, outreach activities such as webinars and training sessions will showcase the diverse applications of VLab 3. Events like the **Blue-Cloud 2026 Hackathon** and the VLIZ Marine Science Day will further help to engage stakeholders and expand the user base.

Policy briefs by VLIZ will also be prepared to inform and guide policymakers during this project.

Collaboration

Scripts from this notebook are also available in EDITO.

Data catalogues

The usage of secondary datasets—those derived from primary data as part of Blue-Cloud activities—will be tracked to monitor the project's reach and impact. Additionally, OGS will advocate for the uptake of VLab 3 by **EMODnet Biology** via the ERDAPP service. All the data from OGS in Gulf of Triest is already available on **ICOS**.

5.5 Exploitation measures committed & planned

The exploitation measures committed by Consortium partners are outlined in Figure 9. Scripts will be published in GitHub in January 2025. Results will be included in Zenodo by VLIZ. It is still under discussion if the data provided by the model could be uptaken by the Marine Data Archive (MDA). In September 2024, VLIZ published the model of the H2020 “Blue-Cloud pilot” project (NPZD model) in the EDITO service catalogue. A new version will be made available for this updated version of the model of the HE “Blue-Cloud 2026” project.

Figure 9. VLab 3 Exploitation measures from 2024 to 2030

5.6 Resources needed to implement the Exploitation Plan

Support for VLab users could be extended after the project ends, provided that additional funding is secured. An estimated 3 PMs/year is required to support a help desk for VLab users during two years after project-end.

6 KER #7 VLAB 4 “Marine Environmental Indicators”

6.1 Description and characterisation of the KER

The Marine Environmental Indicators (MEI) VLab allows users to monitor and assess the environmental status of marine areas and support the decision-making process for ocean management. Multiple data sources are exploited in a unique data analysis service, which will

allow the online computation of indicators through either *Jupyter Notebooks* or a customised web application that exploits the *VRE Analytics Engine* services for computing the indicator’s outputs. The produced indicator outputs can contribute to initiatives such as the Copernicus Marine Ocean State Report or Med-CORDEX.

Figure 10. VLab 4 workflow

Functionalities developed during the pilot phase of Blue-Cloud are being improved, including new algorithms for producing new environmental indicators (Ocean Heat Content, Enhanced Storm Severity Index, Trophic Index and Marine Heat Wave) and new data sources (physics, biogeochemistry, biology, chemical data). The visualisation functionalities of data and the overall user experience will also be improved. During the first two years of the project, new algorithms have been developed, which are being implemented as Jupyter notebooks, in parallel with the development of the user interactive interface for data analytics and display. During the next two years of the project, the focus will be on improving the interoperability of these results with previous services from the Blue-Cloud pilot project and fostering the dissemination and exploitation of the service.

Four KER will be derived from this VLab, namely:

- **KER #7.1:** Implement the algorithm to produce the **Ocean Heat Content (OHC)** with user interaction
- **KER #7.2:** Implement the algorithm to produce the **Marine Heat Wave (MHW)** with user interaction
- **KER #7.3:** Implement the algorithm to produce the **Trophic Index (TRIX)** with user interaction
- **KER #7.4:** Implement the algorithm to produce the **Enhanced Storm Severity Index V2 (SSI V2)** with user interaction

6.1.1 KER #7.1. “Ocean Heat Content (OHC)”

In order to assess the environmental status of marine areas, EOVS datasets produced by the WP3 workbench (WB) 1 on *Physics: temperature & salinity* will be used to get a new OHC estimate. Table 6 provides detailed metadata for the products generated during the use of this indicator. The data, sourced from aggregators such as SeaDataNet, can be seamlessly imported into the VLab environment for direct analysis using DIVAnd.

Table 6. Metadata of OHC data product to be exploited

Input datasets	SeaDataNet World Ocean Database CORA EuroArgo Blue Cloud EOVS dataset (WP3 output)
Analysis method	DIVAnd
Spatial coverage	Mediterranean Sea
Spatial resolution	1/8
Temporal coverage	1955-2024
Temporal resolution	annual
Variables (unit)	Temperature (°C) and OHC (J)
Output file format	NetCDF, PNG
Product relevance	climate studies

6.1.2 KER #7.2. “Marine Heat Wave (MHW)”

In order to assess the environmental status of marine areas, performing online spatio-temporal analysis related to MHW indicators. Table 7 provides detailed metadata for the products generated during the use of this indicator.

Table 7. Metadata of MHW data product to be exploited

Input datasets	Mediterranean Sea - High Resolution L4 Sea Surface Temperature Reprocessed (https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00173), Mediterranean Sea Physics Analysis and Forecast (https://doi.org/10.25423/CMCC/MEDSEA_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_006_013_EAS8)
Spatial coverage	Mediterranean Sea
Spatial resolution	1/24°
Temporal coverage	1981-2024 (for observation) and 2022-2024 (for model data)
Temporal resolution	Daily
Variables (unit)	Sea Surface Temperature (°C)
Output file format	NetCDF, PNG
Product relevance	Decision and policy makers, climate studies

6.1.3 KER #7.3. “Trophic Index (TRIX)”

To assess the environmental status of marine areas, EOv datasets produced by WP3 WB2 on *Eutrophication: chlorophyll, nutrients and oxygen* to calculate climatologies as input to estimate **trohic state index (TRIX)** indicator. Table 8 provides detailed metadata for the products generated during the use of this VLab. The data, sourced from aggregators such as EMODNet Chemistry, can be seamlessly imported into the VLab environment for direct analysis using DIVAnd.

Table 8. Metadata of TRIX data product to be exploited

Input datasets	EMODNet Chemistry (Beta test) Blue Cloud EOv dataset (WP3 workbench eutrophication output)
Analysis method	DIVAnd
Spatial coverage	Territorial waters (12 Nm) for the Mediterranean Sea and the North East Atlantic Sea. 0-100 m depth
Spatial resolution	1/8
Temporal coverage	2003 to 2023
Temporal resolution	Decadal, yearly and seasonal climatologies

Variables (unit)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chlorophyll-a (Chl-a, mg m-3), - Dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN, mg m-3), - Oxygen as absolute percentage deviation from oxygen saturation (DO, %), - Total phosphorus (TP, mg m-3) - TRIX indicator (dimensionless)
Output file format	NetCDF, PNG
Standard vocabularies	NetCDF Climate and Forecast (CF) Metadata Conventions
Product relevance	Decision and policy making, climate studies. The methodology is already embedded in the Italian law: D.Lgs. 152/2006

6.1.4 KER #7.4. “Enhanced Storm Severity Index V2 (SSI V2) ”

The **Enhanced Storm Severity (SSI)** Version 2 service calculates maps and time series of exceptional atmospheric wind or storm circumstances. Individual storms (Event SSI) and specific areas (Area SSI) can be calculated for a given time period and time step (for time series, Table 9). Wind speed threshold data are used to relate the storm severity to specific impact (e.g. sea circulation, coastal damage). Based on the previous version of this service, time and geographical range will be extended to 80 years for Europe and North Atlantic. However, it should be noted that due to health issues, the initial partners of this service were not able to participate in the writing of this document. Exploitation pathways may thus change if there is a change of partners. This is currently under discussion.

Table 9. Metadata of SSI V2 data product to be exploited

Input datasets	ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1940 to present from Copernicus C3S Climate Data Store (CDS) (Available at https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels)
Spatial coverage	Europe and North Atlantic (North 73, West - 60, South 30 and East 48)
Temporal coverage	1940 to present
Temporal resolution	Hourly
Variables (unit)	Wind speed
Output file format	Net CDF, PNG

6.2 Asset owner(s)

Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (CMCC) is the leader of this Vlab. The Vlab partners are the **Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale (OGS)** in Italy, the **Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia in Italy (INGV)** and the **Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut (KNMI)** in the Netherlands.

6.3 Target Users

Figure 11. VLab 4 Target users

This VLab provides a suite of marine environmental indicators through advanced analysis and production workflows (Figure 11).

This VLab provides a suite of MEI through advanced analysis and production workflows. The primary target users are **researchers**, particularly those specialising in oceanography, environmental science and climate change. Existing data catalogues, such as the **Copernicus Marine Ocean Monitoring Indicators**, are foundational resources for these marine indicators and are being used in this VLab.

Collaboration with policymakers is a cornerstone of this initiative, ensuring that scientific knowledge informs the development of effective policies and practices. This collaboration is crucial for monitoring the marine environment, safeguarding its natural and human assets, and shaping strategies for sustainable use. Key stakeholders of this VLab include **Governmental Environmental Agencies** (e.g., Italy's **ARPA**), managers of **Marine Protected Areas, Municipalities, and Port Authorities**.

Furthermore, this VLab addresses the needs of a wide array of economic stakeholders. These include professionals such as **marina managers, aquaculture and fisheries operators**, and representatives from industries reliant on the ocean, such as oil and gas. The data products support **Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG)** reporting for industries, financial institutions (e.g., investors assessing risk), and sustainability consultancies (e.g., **KPMG, Deloitte, PwC, EY**).

Additionally, MPA managers and environmental NGOs can enhance their advocacy and management strategies using the VLab's data products. By providing actionable insights, the VLab empowers diverse stakeholders to manage resources sustainably, plan new developments responsibly, and strengthen marine environmental protection efforts.

6.4 Exploitation pathways & milestones

Figure 12. Vlab 4 Exploitation pathways

To ensure the Blue-Cloud 2026 platform is readily accessible to identified target users, as outlined in Section 6.3, various measures will be implemented to address barriers and enhance engagement (Figure 12).

VLabs Access and Support

To ensure the Blue-Cloud 2026 platform is **accessible** to target users, as outlined in Section 6.3, various measures will be implemented to overcome barriers and enhance engagement. First of all, free and open-access with CC BY licence will be applied to all resources available in the VLab. Support will be offered on a best effort basis.

Community Engagement and Outreach

Researchers may encounter challenges such as unfamiliarity with the web tool or the Python skills needed for Jupyter notebooks. To address these, the project will implement several strategies, including the **publication** of scientific papers, and **outreach** through events such as the **Blue-Cloud 2026 webinars**, **Blue-Cloud 2026 Hackathon**, **GlobalCoast (CoastPredict) conferences**, and the **Blue-Cloud Training Academy**. User experience improvements are also being made to the web tool, adding features like dynamic maps and time-series **visualisations** to enhance interactivity. The tool will remain open access and freely available, with proposals to integrate it into international initiatives such as "GlobalCoast" or "CoastPredict".

To promote VLab 4 within the scientific community, scientific papers will be published as a means of outreach. The platform will also serve as a **training resource** for students and early-career scientists, with user guides and handbooks readily available both on the platform and in VLab 4.

While current marine data catalogues are valuable resources, they have limitations that may require additional training for users, particularly those using Python-based Jupyter notebooks. Furthermore, it is essential that users of the VLab should be cautious and validate the outputs generated when using the Jupyter notebooks.

VLab 4 will facilitate a Blue-Cloud **Training Academy** (<https://blue-cloud.org/training-academy>), following the model established for previous VLabs. Dissemination activities will include participating in conferences such as IMDIS, EGU and OneOcean, and releasing scientific publications to engage the research community. These have the goal to increase publicity about Blue-Cloud 2026 VLab 4 and hopefully contribute to its long-term viability.

Collaboration with Blue Economy stakeholders will be pursued through targeted webinars, showcasing how VLab 4 can meet their specific needs. Products and services will be aligned with the Taskforce on **Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD) & Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD)** frameworks, and the platform's front end will offer tools for instant data insights.

6.5 Exploitation measures committed & planned

The exploitation measures committed by Consortium partners are outlined in Figure 13. Until 2024, this Vlab has been building requirements from target communities for each indicator. In 2025, it is planned to participate in webinars and hackathons organised by the Blue-Cloud consortium. Training sessions will be given, and partners will participate in conferences to promote this VLab to other European and international projects. In 2026, a peer-reviewed scientific paper will be written by all partners. Scripts will be published in GitHub and results uploaded to Zenodo. INGV will propose to include the BC OHC estimate into **Copernicus Marine Service Ocean Monitoring Indicators catalogue**. Ingestion of data products by all partners in other repositories might be available on request. One training will be offered on request, after the project completion.

Committed Exploitation Measures

Figure 13. Vlab 4 Exploitation measures from 2024 to 2030

7 KER #8 VLAB 5 “Global Fisheries Atlas”

7.1 Description and characterisation of the KER

Global Fisheries Atlas VLab 5 provides a hands-on learning experience to explore the use of the Global Tuna Atlas and GRSF catalogue for **studying and managing fish populations**. The VLab allows users to navigate and analyse the data provided by these tools, including creating maps and visualisations of tuna distribution and migration patterns. Overall, this VLab will provide a comprehensive and interactive learning experience that will enhance global understanding of tuna biology and management.

Table 10. Metadata of VLab 5 data product to be exploited

Input datasets	Georeferenced catches (1 deg/ 5 deg/ All)
Spatial coverage	Atlantic and Western-Central Pacific Oceans (or FAO major areas and stock assessment areas)
Temporal coverage	1918-2019
Variables (unit)	Weight (metric tons) or number of fish, depending on the gears concerned, with longline catches typically available in numbers only
Output file format	CSV
Standard vocabularies	<u>FIRMS Global Tuna Atlas (GTA) - All Information Collections</u>

7.2 Asset owner(s)

The **Institut de Recherche pour le Développement (IRD)** is the leader of this VLab. Partners are the **Foundation for Research and Technology (FORTH)** in Greece.

7.3 Target Users

Figure 14. VLab 5 Target users

VLab 5 serves diverse user groups—primary, intermediary, and tertiary—by leveraging its marine science and data integration capabilities. Primary users include scientists and data catalogues, each with distinct roles, needs, and objectives (Figure 14). The early adopters for this consolidated group are **scientists** and **regional fisheries management organisations (RFMOs)**. This work will be advertised by the FIRMS network (**FAO** and **RFMOs**). All these users will use the open access of this public data, code and runtime environment.

Scientists

The VLab is targeted at **fisheries scientists** which can use the Global Fisheries Atlas (GFA) for accessing updated time series of catch and fishing effort data to drive stock assessment and population dynamics models. **Marine biologists** will also find relevant data about species distribution that are key for ecological research. **Climate change analysts** can study the impact of climate on fisheries by running cross domain analysis with ocean temperature data, salinity levels, and other climate-related factors. Other target users are **modellers** (e.g. CC impact), **data managers** and scientists studying **biodiversity**.

Data repositories, the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS), **Global Biodiversity Information (GBIF)**, **FAO fisheries data catalogue**, **INSPIRE** and **ODATIS** (French national) are all data catalogues that will be targeted as users of VLab 5. **Data managers in the marine domain, standardisation bodies** and beyond might be interested in implementing similar data management plans for other kinds of data.

Further building on the work of VLab 5, other (**tertiary**) users will benefit from its tools & services:

Blue Economy Actors and Policy Makers

The VLab can be leveraged to inform **policy makers, commercial fisheries, and conservation organisations**. Regional fisheries management bodies, and other policymakers can utilise the GFA for helping craft legislation and marine spatial planning. **Operators, fisheries managers, and industry representatives** can leverage the GFA for strategic planning, sustainable practice adoption. **Fishing fleets and the seafood industry** e.g. canneries would also benefit from the services of this VLab.

Conservation Organizations and **NGOs** would benefit from detailed fisheries data for habitat protection efforts, biodiversity conservation strategies, and environmental impact assessments.

7.4 Exploitation pathways & milestones

Figure 15. Vlab 5 Exploitation pathways

To ensure the Blue-Cloud 2026 platform is readily accessible to identified target users, as outlined in Section 7.3, various measures will be implemented to address barriers and enhance engagement (Figure 15).

VLabs Access and Support

VLab 5 will be open to all users beyond the Blue-Cloud Consortium, providing unrestricted access both during and after the project's completion. The VLab results will be self-explanatory and well-documented with appropriate metadata. Support for users will be provided through RMarkdown tutorials, GitHub repositories, webinars, and direct contact with key stakeholders (IRD, FORTH, FAO, depending on the product). Additionally, the VLab will continue to be supported by key contacts for any questions or technical assistance.

Community Engagement

VLab 5 will engage a wide range of users, including researchers, industries, governmental agencies, and citizens. The platform will offer long-term time series and reproducible data formats, and users will be encouraged to interact with the system through a variety of accessible tools. Specialized training and webinars will ensure that users from different sectors, including the Blue Economy, can effectively use the VLab. These initiatives will be targeted to increase global visibility and engagement, such as workshops organized by Indian Tuna organizations, where learners can analyze datasets in a shared R environment.

- **Publications:** a data paper will be published by FIRMS (IRD, FAO, and Tuna RFMOs) in 2025. DOIs will be assigned to datasets and code, ensuring proper citation and dissemination. The results will also be made available through established data infrastructures like Zenodo, FAO Fisheries Data Catalog, Blue-Cloud VLab, and RFMOs working groups. These efforts will support broader scientific adoption and encourage further contributions to the community.
- **Webinars and Other Interactive Sessions:** Webinars and workshops will be organized to demonstrate how to use VLab 5, including a workshop on creating dockerized R Shiny apps, metadata publication workflows, and data analysis in R. These events will offer hands-on learning experiences for users and will highlight how VLab 5 can be applied in various domains, such as fisheries data analysis, to increase user engagement. These sessions will also be advertised at scientific conferences like IMDIS and FOSS4G.

Outreach Initiatives

VLab 5 will be promoted through targeted outreach initiatives, including workshops, conferences, and webinars aimed at researchers, industries, and policymakers. By participating in conferences and specialized groups like IMDIS and FOSS4G, the VLab will reach a broader audience. Additionally, collaborative efforts will focus on supporting the specific needs of Blue Economy actors, industries, and governmental agencies through customized data exploration, dashboards, and RShiny apps.

Collaboration

VLab 5 will foster collaboration with a variety of stakeholders, including Blue Economy actors, industries, and governmental agencies. Custom data exploration tools and visualization platforms, such as RShiny apps, will be developed to meet the specific needs of these sectors. The platform will also engage with citizens by providing accessible visualizations and simplified tools. Collaborations will extend to data-sharing networks such as EMODNet Biology and FAO to

ensure that VLab 5 products meet relevant standards and regulations. This will be linked to the same DOIs.

Data Catalogues

VLab 5 will continue to leverage data catalogues such as Zenodo and the FAO Fisheries Data Catalog, ensuring that datasets remain available and up-to-date. Interoperability will be a key focus, allowing data to be integrated and shared across various platforms. Restricted access DOIs will be used for sensitive data, ensuring privacy and compliance with EMODNet Biology regulations. The results of VLab 5 will be integrated into EMODNet Biology with the necessary consent and guidelines from the FAO. This will be linked to the same DOIs.

7.5 Exploitation measures committed & planned

After building requirements with main users i.e. UN FAO, selected scripts will be updated in **GitHub** to implement good coding, data management practices and the continuous integration pipelines. These main releases are assigned as DOIs on Zenodo and also shared on FAO Fisheries Catalogue.

Webinars, trainings and a hackathon will be organised in 2025. An **Indian Ocean Tuna Commission Working Party on Data Collection and Statistics (IOTC WPDCS)** working paper will be published each year and a data paper will be published in 2025 after validation of the data. The results of this Vlab will be integrated into **EMODNet Biology** in 2025, after making sure all requirements are met.

Committed Exploitation Measures

Figure 16. Vlab 5 Exploitation measures from 2024 to 2030

7.6 Resources needed to implement the Exploitation Plan

Without funding, IRD commits to allocating a researcher with a dedication of 2PM/year to support the yearly update of the Global Tuna Atlas products (FIRMS level 0 and upper levels of processing), improving the code of the workflow and shiny apps and help desk for VLab users during 5 years after project-end. With funding, a full-time engineer would be hired to allocate more time.

FAO coordinates the work of FIRMS to ensure the update of Global Tuna Atlas level 0, discuss the endorsement of upper levels of processing (levels 1 and 2) and makes these products available on iMarine as well as its Spatial Data Infrastructure (hosted on Google Cloud). Depending on funding the time that FAO can allocate would also vary.

FORTH being the technical coordinator of GRSF is responsible for the construction and maintenance of the GRSF Knowledge Base, as well as the publishing of its records in the VLab catalogue. FORTH commits to allocate the required resources to keep the VLab contents up to date by periodically publishing or updating records in the catalogue.

The human and economic resources needed are:

- Help desk for VLab users: 0.5 PM to 2 PM/year
- Update of the Vlab products including data generation workflow and outputs (FIRMS level 0 dataset and upper levels of processing) and shiny apps: 1 PM up to 6 PM /year
- RStudio or Shiny apps servers hosting with pre-installed virtual environments: 0.5 PM up to 4 PM/year
- Enhance GRSF with more stocks and fisheries records (as they are approved by GRSF administrators): 0.5 PM/year for publishing approved records
- Refresh approved GRSF records with updated information from their original sources: 0.5 PM/year for updating records

8 Key Performance Indicators and Targets (2026-2030)

Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for all the VLab will be:

1. **Number of Registered Users:** The total count of users registered within the VLab. This will be tracked via the platform on D4Science (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Users use of the platform for one of the VLab. Users are categorized by countries, by platform they're using, by duration of use.

2. **Scientific Engagement:** The number of scientists or individuals utilising the VLab, particularly those employing the data for research purposes.
3. **Regular User Metrics:** It is crucial to monitor not only overall usage but also the frequency of regular users, as consistent engagement is a key indicator of success.
4. **Stakeholder Interaction:** Engagement from stakeholders, including governmental and non-governmental organisations, will be assessed. Each reference to thematic issues, such as eutrophication, will be considered a success indicator.
5. **Cross-Platform Access:** Users accessing the VLab from external platforms, such as RShiny, will also be tracked to measure the reach and impact of the VLab.
6. **Number of attendees of webinars/trainings/hackatons**
7. Number of references to the VLAB in **scientific publications** including:
 - o Data product publication on dataset journals
 - o Workflow publication on Journal of Data Science and Analytics
 - o Number of views or downloads of DOIs published on Zenodo
 - o Number of citations in the literature (from DOIs)

Success targets are:

- One scientific publication on each thematic
- Long-term use of Blue-Cloud 2026 Vlabs and use in other projects e.g. Aquarius for Vlab 1 (See Section 3.4.)

9 Joint opportunities for exploitation across Blue-Cloud KERs

9.1 Joint exploitation opportunities across Blue-Cloud V Labs

During the development of the V Labs, several cross-exploitation opportunities have been identified, which will be further explored in the coming months. These opportunities underscore the value of a collaborative environment, where research findings can be shared and repurposed by other researchers to foster and support new scientific advancements. The planned exploitation initiatives between V Labs are outlined below.

Each V Lab was designed to support scientists in their work. However, by integrating the V Labs, we aim to enhance their collective capacity to address complex research questions with greater precision while facilitating streamlined access to datasets for applied scientific endeavors.

1. “Integration of Coastal observations along Europe” (KER #4 VLab 1) will cooperate with “Coastal Currents from Observations” (KER#5 VLab 2). Both of these V Labs are using HF radar data from the **European High Frequency Radar Node (EU HFR)**. The EU HFR Node is managing data from European HFR networks and integrates and delivers US HFR network data to the aforementioned data portals. In particular, the EU HFR Node implements the functions of data acquisition and harvesting, QC, validation/assessment, NRT data delivery and historical data distribution with different reprocessing levels. Coastal current data could be integrated into coastal observations data to build products that would meet specific requirements for governments. This will be created for an overlap area between the two datasets, situated in the Mediterranean Sea.
2. This combined coastal observations and coastal currents dataset could be linked to the Global Fisheries Atlas focusing on tuna population and migration (KER #8 VLab 5). Many factors contribute to tuna migration happening across the entire Atlantic Ocean to feed off the coast of Europe (Fromentin & Powers, 2005). Information gathered from VLab 1 and VLab 2 together provide data on temperature, currents, ocean conditions, continental shelf break and slope. Specific products could be developed to help researchers better

understand tuna migration and therefore sustain fisheries in the long-term and in changing conditions.

9.2 Joint exploitation with Blue-Cloud Workbenches

“Marine Environmental Indicators: OHC” (KER #7.1 VLab 4) and “Physics: temperature & salinity” (KER #1 WB 1) will collaborate to create essential ocean variables that can be used as environmental indicators. The workflow is indicated in Figure 18.

Figure 18. Adapted from Data Value Chain (Simoncelli et al., 2022)

“Marine Environmental Indicators: TRIX” (KER #7.3 VLab 4) and “Eutrophication Data Collection” (KER #2 WB 2) will collaborate to create climatologies from the harmonized and validated essential ocean variables (Harmonized & Validated EOVS) dataset developed in WB 2. With this data, climatologies with DIVAnd will be produced and then used to calculate the **Trophic State Index (TRIX)**, Vollenweider, R.A. et al 1998). This TRIX index will be calculated and made available to users via Jupyter notebooks. The core code will be implemented on the CCP to be ingested and visualized into the already existing web service **MEI generator** (VLab 4) along with the other services.

10 Conclusion

The Blue-Cloud 2026 project represents a pioneering initiative in advancing marine data interoperability and fostering collaborative research through a suite of innovative virtual labs. This exploitation plan outlines strategic actions to maximise the impact and sustainability of these VLabs, ensuring that they effectively support the research, policy, and blue economy sectors beyond the project's duration. By promoting data accessibility, enhancing digital services, and fostering cross-fertilization between VLabs, it will enable stakeholders across Europe to leverage open marine data for critical insights into coastal observations, coastal currents, carbon-plankton dynamics, marine environmental indicators and global fisheries.

Each VLab has been designed with specific primary, intermediary & end-user needs and scientific challenges in mind, supporting fields such as ocean modelling, fisheries, and environmental monitoring. Through coordinated efforts with European and international stakeholders, Blue-Cloud 2026 aims to establish these VLabs as essential digital resources, integrated within the broader EOSC framework, EDITO, and accessible to a wide user base.

Through the exploitation measures outlined in this plan, Blue-Cloud 2026 sets the ground to ensure the usability and legacy of these virtual labs, ultimately contributing to enhance marine knowledge, and to enable a more resilient, data-informed approach to ocean governance and sustainability.

11 Bibliography

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